

A Love Letter for Criminology Students

Alexis Mari D. Prado

Instructor I

Laguna State Polytechnic University

Criminology students are left with two choices they could make after graduating from the four (4)-year degree program: Continue reviewing for the board exam or to survive.

Given the limited job market and scarce opportunities that the Criminology profession is currently facing, many are obliged to enter a different career market mismatched with the abilities they have honed over the course of 4 years of struggling to obtain a Criminology degree- as if they were entering a gladiator's arena to be butchered. But with a different frame of mind - to survive daily and reach for their ultimate goal.

There has been an exponential upsurge in the production of Criminologists in recent years compared to the past decade before the then-President Rodrigo Roa Duterte announced a charming increase in salary for police officers, a career path where many Criminologists has dreamt to pursue. In addition, new degree programs under the College of Criminal Justice were launched and offered by Higher Education Institutions including, the Bachelor of Forensic Science and Bachelor of Science in Industrial Security Management programs which creates a tight competition within a withering job market.

While many board passers patiently and successfully find employment aligned to their competencies and passion, some fail and retreat to an occupation where a Registered Criminologist cannot practice being a "Criminologist" as prescribed in Section 5 of the Republic Act No. 11131 or the "Philippine Criminology Profession Act of 2018".

Several Registered Criminologists prepare their credentials and take qualifying exams in public safety agencies they wish to pursue but in reality, they must also be prepared in failure as there is an outpour of professionals from other college programs who are intending to enter the same job market as theirs. This is where survival of the fittest and the most confident thrives.

Even so, private industries providing and needing services pertaining to safety, security and investigation values commitment, leadership and passion -exceptional virtues only a handful of professionals can possess and not bound by any professional license. These are the arenas where Registered Criminologists find and accustom themselves with a diverse range of team members from different backgrounds whose endeavor is to resolve the contemporaneous emergence of technologies, processes and dynamic developments in delivery of services to clients and consumers.

It is not well known to many that majority of students who enter the Criminology program came from distinct middle to working class social backgrounds and have little-to-no experience of handling personal computers and laptops. Initially in their minds, they want to contribute to the society by instilling peace, order and restore the reputation of the criminal justice system of our country.

To attain that goal, a big step upward the ladder carried on by the weight of hope, shall be surged forward together with the never-ending quest for learning new knowledge, imperishable principles and a passionate heart dedicated for civic duty.

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